

On 4-Keto-3:4-Dihydroisocoumarin

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Experiments to synthesise Perkin's 5:6-dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin have been described. 4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin has been synthesised by an adaptation of Curtius reaction and also by chromic acid oxidation of 3:4-dihydroisocoumarin. A number of condensation products of 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin with aromatic aldehydes including Zincke's aldehyde have also been described. The *m*-methoxybenzylidene derivative was converted into 6'-methoxyindeno (2':3':3:4)isocoumarin which represents a new ring system.

By systematic degradation of tetrahydroberberine methochloride, Perkin¹ had isolated 2-hydroxymethyl-3:4-dimethoxyphenylacetaldehyde and 5:6-dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (I). A synthesis of the former has been published² and in this paper we describe experiments designed to synthesise the latter. The syntheses of 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin and its derivatives have been carried out by a number of recent workers³⁻⁵ who have, in general, carried out an acid-catalysed cyclisation of *o*-alkoxycarbonyl diazoacetophenone secured from the related half-ester acid chloride or the related phthalic anhydride and diazomethane.

1. W. H. Perkin, (Jun.), *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 958.
2. J. N. Chatterjee, B. K. Banerjee and H. C. Jha, *Chem. Ber.* 1965, 98, 3279.
3. P. McC Duggleby and G. Holt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 3580.
4. A. Bhati, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 1183.
5. L. Reichel and W. Hanzpel, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, 59, 7470.

For the synthesis of (I), the requisite half-ester (II) was prepared⁶ from hemipinic acid. Although the compound readily formed hemipinic anhydride by the action of phosphorus pentachloride or thionyl chloride, the desired acid chloride was prepared by the action of oxalyl chloride in the cold and then converted into the diazoketone (III). This, on treatment with warm dilute sulphuric acid, gave a ketone which was recognised as (IV). In contrast, the isomeric diazoketone (VI) derived from the half-ester (V) readily furnished 7:8-dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (VII) which had the requisite i.r. spectrum (lactone carbonyl absorption at 5.85μ and aromatic carbonyl absorption at 5.96μ).

The anomalous result cited above can be reconciled in terms of the mechanism of cyclisation of the diazoacetyl group with the neighbouring ether or ester function⁷. In each case an oxonium ion is formed as an intermediate as a result of nucleophilic attack of the lone electron pairs of oxygen as shown. The intermediate then loses methanol as a result of nucleophilic attack of water. In (III) the diazoacetyl group is flanked on both sides by an ester and an ether function and it is the latter that reacts in preference because it is a more powerful nucleophile than the carbonyl oxygen.

In the event, we were led to explore other possible routes leading to (I) and as a preliminary measure, the study of oxidation of 3:4-dihydroisocoumarin was undertaken. Dihydroisocoumarin was conveniently prepared in quantity from isocoumarin by catalytic hydrogenation. This hydrogenation is attended with a little hydrogenolysis yielding *o*-ethyl benzoic acid⁸. Controlled oxidation of dihydroisocoumarin with chromic acid afforded a small yield of 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin but an adaptation of this procedure to the synthesis of (I) from 5:6-dimethoxy-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (VIII) failed due to the preferential formation of 5:6-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid resulting from oxidation at the alternative methylene group.

A more fruitful route involved the Curtius reaction with isocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (IX). This was converted into the acid chloride and then by conventional method

6. V. M. Rodionov and A. M. Fejorova, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1944, **38**, 4260.

7. A. Bose and P. Yates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4703.

8. S. M. McElvain, R. D. Bright and P. R. Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 1558; J. Meinwald, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1955, **49**, 5318.

into the azide (X) and thence to the urethane (XI). When the latter was boiled with hydrochloric acid, a crystalline product was isolated which was recognised as (XII) arising

from self-condensation of 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin. L. Reichel and W. Hampel⁵ claimed to have obtained naphthacene 5, 6, 11, 12-tetrone from 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin by the action of 20% aqueous hydrochloric acid. No such product was isolated by us. On employing dilute sulphuric acid 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin was isolated and similarly, we prepared 6:7-dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin which was also independently secured from *m*-hemipinic acid.

Application of this route to the synthesis of (I) from XI, (methoxy groups at 5 and 6 positions) however, has unaccountably failed. The urethane proved remarkably stable. On prolonged treatment with dilute sulphuric acid, a nitrogenous product, m.p. 115° was isolated in a small yield and a thorough search of the reaction mixture did not reveal the presence of (I) even in traces.

4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin readily condenses with aromatic aldehydes in presence of acids or secondary bases to give the corresponding arylidene derivatives. A number of these arylidene derivatives have been prepared which are described in Table I. 4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin has also been condensed with Zincke's aldehyde⁶ in pyridine to give

(XIII) which was obtained in glistening violet needles. The *m*-methoxybenzylidene derivative (XIV) was catalytically reduced to the corresponding dihydro derivative and then

cyclodehydrated by polyphosphoric acid to give 6'-methoxyindeno (2':3'-3:4) isocoumarin (XV) which represents a new ring system. This condensed isocoumarin furnished the related isocarbostyryl (XV, CO-NH-in place of CO-O-) in quantitative yield on heating with alcoholic ammonia. It may be added that the synthesis of indeno (3':2'—3:4) isocoumarin and its derivatives has already been effected in this laboratory¹⁰.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. The i.r. spectra were determined in KBr pellet in Perkin Elmer Infracord apparatus (Model 237).

3:4-Dihydroisocoumarin: A solution of isocoumarin (9.0 g.) in acetic acid (50 c.c.) was hydrogenated in presence of palladised charcoal (0.5 g., 30%) at room temperature. The hydrogenation was complete in two hours. After filtration, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the residual oil was extracted with ether and the ether solution washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. 3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (7.5 g.) was obtained at 132-34°/3 mm. as a colourless liquid. The bicarbonate solution on acidification gave *o*-ethylbenzoic acid (0.05 g.), m.p. 64° (carboxyl absorption at 5.95 μ) and further confirmed by the preparation of the amide, m.p. 153° (lit.¹¹, m.p. 151-53°).

4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin: A solution of chromic acid (0.62 g.) in water (0.5 c.c.) and acetic acid (2 c.c.) was added dropwise with stirring to 3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.3 g.) in acetic acid (0.5 c.c.) maintained at 25°. After stirring for 3 hours at room temperature, an equal volume of water was added and the mixture extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with NaHCO₃ solution. On evaporation of the solvent, an oily residue was obtained which was taken up in ether and extracted with sodium hydroxide solution (1%). The alkaline extract on acidification gave 4-keto-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin

10. J. N. Chatterjea and H. Mukherjee, *This Journal*, 1960, 37, 443.

11. G. Giese, *Chem. Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2534.

(0.1 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 149-50° (lit.³, m.p. 145-45.5°, lit.¹², m.p. 149°) giving 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 241° (lit.³, m.p. 225-27°) from alcohol. (Found: C, 52.60; H, 3.15, calculated for $C_{13}H_6O_6N_4$; C, 52.64; H, 2.93%). The semicarbazone crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 259-60° (decomp.). (Found: C, 54.70; H, 4.30; $C_{10}H_8O_2N_2$ requires: C, 54.80; H, 4.11%).

The bicarbonate extract on acidification gave homophthalic acid. When the above oxidation was performed at 50° or at the temperature of boiling water, no improvement in yield resulted.

5:6-Dimethoxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin: 5:6-Dimethoxyisocoumarin² (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (30 c.c.) was hydrogenated in presence of 30% palladised charcoal at room temperature and normal pressure, when one mole of hydrogen was absorbed. After filtration, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure when 5:6-dimethoxy-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin was obtained in quantitative yield, m.p. 65-66° (from ethyl acetate-light petroleum). (Found: C, 63.35; H, 5.68. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 63.46; H, 5.76%). The i.r. spectrum showed carbonyl absorption at 5.80 μ .

Oxidation of 5:6-Dimethoxy-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin with Chromic Acid: A solution of chromic acid (0.65 g.) in water (0.6 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (2.5 c.c.) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of 5:6-dimethoxy-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.28 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) maintained at 30° by occasional cooling of the reaction vessel in ice-bath. After stirring for 3 hours more, water was added, extracted with chloroform, the extract washed with sodium carbonate, water and dried ($MgSO_4$). On evaporation of the solvent, an oily residue was obtained which was taken up in ether and extracted with sodium hydroxide solution (1%). The alkaline extract on acidification afforded 5:6-dimethoxy-homophthalic acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 194-95° (lit.¹³, m.p. 196°).

α -Methylester of Hemipinic Acid: Hemipinic anhydride (1.0 g.) was refluxed with dry methanol (8.0 c.c.) for four hours on water bath. After working up in the usual manner, the ester was obtained as needles, m.p. 146°, after crystallising from benzene (lit.⁵, m.p. 149-50°).

β -Methylester of Hemipinic Acid: Hemipinic acid (1.5 g.), absolute methanol (7.5 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (0.52 c.c.) were refluxed for forty five minutes. After working up in the usual manner, the ester (0.8 g.), m.p. 147° was obtained as prisms after crystallising from benzene (lit.¹⁴, m.p. 149°).

7:8-Dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin. The α -methylester of hemipinic acid (m.p. 145-46°, 0.5 g.) was suspended in dry benzene (1 c.c.) and treated with oxalyl chloride (2 c.c.) in cold for two hours, during which time the ester dissolved. The excess of benzene and oxalyl chloride were removed in vacuum at the room temperature. The residual oily acid chloride was dissolved in dry ether (10 c.c.) and was added in usual manner to an ice-cold ethereal solution of diazomethane (derived from 7.0 g. of nitrosomethyl urea) and the mixture left overnight in the refrigerator. The diazo-ketone separated as large prisms (0.25 g.), m.p. 142° (decomp.). These were collected and heated with sulphuric acid (3%,

12. E. B. Knott, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 402.

13. S. N. Chakravarty and M. Swaminathan, *This Journal*, 1934, 11, 101.

14. R. Wegscheider, *Monatsh*, 1897, 18, 641.

20 c.c.) for one hour on water bath. The diazo-ketone slowly decomposed with evolution of nitrogen. On cooling 7:8-*dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin* separated in crystalline state, crystallising from alcohol in needles, m.p. 157-58°. (Found: C, 60.10, 59.81; H, 5.41, 5.62. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires: C, 59.46; H, 4.55 (%). The i.r. spectrum showed absorption at 5.84 μ (lactone carbonyl), (aromatic ketone) 5.96 μ . The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid as shining orange-red plates, m.p. 240-41°. (Found: N, 13.75. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.93%).

7-Methoxy-4-methoxycarbonylcoumarone-3: A solution of β -methyl ester of hemipinic acid (0.6 g., m.p. 147°) in dry benzene (2 c.c.) was treated at 0° with oxalyl chloride (2.5 c.c.) and the mixture was left for 6 hours at room temperature during which time the acid completely dissolved. On removal of the volatile matter in vacuum at room temperature, a small quantity of hemipinic anhydride (m.p. 163°) separated. The acid chloride was dissolved in dry ether (leaving the anhydride which did not dissolve) and added slowly to cold ethereal diazomethane (from 5.0 g. of nitrosomethyl urea) and the mixture left overnight. The resulting diazo-ketone was isolated as an oil. This underwent exothermic decomposition on treatment with sulphuric acid (3%). The mixture was then warmed on the water-bath, cooled and extracted with ether.

4-Methoxycarbonyl-7-methoxycoumaran-3-one. was obtained as an oil characterised by a crystalline semicarbazone, m.p. 200° (decomp.) from alcohol. (Found: C, 51.43; H, 4.72, $C_{11}H_{13}O_5N_3$ requires: C, 51.62; H, 4.66%).

Mono-ethyl ester of *m*-Hemipinic Acid. *m*-Hemipinic anhydride (1.0 g.) was refluxed with absolute ethanol (50 c.c.) for half an hour. After working up in the usual way the half ester was obtained as crystals m.p. 127°, after crystallising from benzene (lit.¹⁵, m.p. 127°).

6:7-Dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin: The foregoing half-ester (0.9 g.) was suspended in dry benzene (1 c.c.) and treated with oxalyl chloride (1.0 c.c.) and kept at room temperature for twenty four hours. The oily acid chloride was dissolved in dry ether (10 c.c.) and was added to an ice-cold ethereal solution of diazomethane (derived from 3.0 g. of nitrosomethyl urea) and the mixture left overnight in the refrigerator. The diazoketone, obtained as an oil, was warmed with 3% sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) for one hour on water bath. 6:7-Dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin, separated crystallising from alcohol in light brown needles, m.p. 246°. (Found: C, 59.32; H, 4.76. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 59.40; H, 4.56%). The i.r. spectrum showed lactone carbonyl absorption at 5.85 μ and aromatic ketonic absorption at 5.96 μ . The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallised from nitrobenzene as shining red plates, m.p. 251-52°. (Found: N, 13.52. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.93%).

4-Carboethoxyaminoisocoumarin. Isocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (0.56 g.) suspended in dry benzene (1.0 c.c.) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (3.0 c.c.) and a drop of pyridine for 30 minutes. The resulting acid chloride was obtained as crystalline solid, m.p. 118-19°. This was dissolved in dry acetone (20 c.c.) at 0° and to it was added dropwise a solution of sodium azide (0.4 g.) in water (2.0 c.c.) with stirring. After ten minutes, water (32 c.c.) was added when the crude azide (0.8 g.) separated as brown solid, m.p. 109-10° (with gas evolution). It was dried by keeping overnight in a vacuum desiccator. Next day, the above azide (0.8 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) and refluxed for one and half hours

when it decomposed with evolution of nitrogen. Excess of alcohol was removed under reduced pressure when crude 4-carbethoxyaminoisocoumarin (0.7 g.) was obtained which on crystallisation from alcohol was obtained as needles, m.p. 137-38°. (Found: C, 61.40; H, 5.10; N, 6.1. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 61.80; H, 4.75; N, 6.01%).

Reaction of 4-Carbethoxyaminoisocoumarin with conc. Hydrochloric Acid. The urethane (0.1 g.) was taken with conc. hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) and refluxed for 20 minutes. A crystalline mass soon separated which was collected and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 241°. This analysed for self-condensation product (XII) of 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (described below). (Found: C, 69.80; H, 3.90. $C_{16}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 70.59; H, 3.29%).

Self-condensation of 4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin: 4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.1 g.) obtained by the method of Duggleby and Holt³ was taken with conc. hydrochloric acid (1.5 c.c.) and heated on water bath for an hour. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with water and the precipitated self-condensation product separated. This crystallised from alcohol in slightly yellow needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above product 241° (no depression).

4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin: The urethane (0.1 g.) was refluxed with dilute sulphuric acid (5 c.c.; 2%) for 48 hours. The mixture was cooled and the precipitated solid, m.p. 149-50° was identified as 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin by the preparation of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (m.p. 238-39°). The i.r. spectrum showed the expected absorptions at 5.80 μ and 5.97 μ .

6:7-Dimethoxy-4-carbethoxyaminoisocoumarin: 6:7-Dimethoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid¹⁶ (0.5 g.), dry benzene (1.0 c.c.) and oxalyl chloride (1.5 c.c.) were refluxed for 4 hours when all the acid went into solution. The excess of oxalyl chloride was removed under vacuum and the last traces removed by washing with benzene followed by its removal in vacuum. It was dissolved in dry acetone (40 c.c.) at 0° and treated dropwise with a solution of sodium azide (0.48 g.) in water (2.5 c.c.) with stirring. After about ten minutes water was added, when the azide, m.p. 210° (gas evolution) separated.

Next day, the dried azide (0.3 g.) was refluxed with dry ethanol (5 c.c.) for one and half hours when evolution of nitrogen was observed below the boiling point of alcohol. Alcohol was then removed under reduced pressure when crude 6:7-dimethoxy-4-carbethoxyaminoisocoumarin (0.25 g.) was obtained, m.p. 191-92°. After repeated crystallisation from alcohol, it was obtained as needles, m.p. 194-95°. (Found: C, 57.44; H, 4.10. $C_{16}H_{15}O_5N$ requires C, 57.30; H, 5.1%). (Carbonyl absorptions at 5.90 and 5.80 μ). (NH—absorption at 3.06 μ).

6:7-Dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin: The urethane (0.1 g.) was refluxed with sulphuric acid (2 c.c.; 10%) for two hours. On cooling the crystals of 6:7-dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin separated which was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 245-46° and had superimposable i.r. spectrum with the specimen obtained earlier by a different method.

Attempted Synthesis of 5:6-Dimethoxy-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.

5:6-Dimethoxy-4-carbethoxyaminoisocoumarin: *5:6-Dimethoxyisocoumarin-4-car-*

boxylic acid (0.5 g.) suspended in dry benzene (1.0 c.c.) was treated with oxalyl chloride (1.0 c.c.) in cold and left for four hours at room temperature during which time all the acid dissolved. This was worked up in usual manner and the oily acid chloride was taken in dry acetone (5.3 c.c.) at 0°, and to it was added dropwise a solution of sodium azide (0.2 g.) in water (1.0 c.c.) with vigorous stirring. After ten minutes, water (16 c.c.) was added when the crude azide separated as brown solid (0.27 g.), m.p. 104° (decomp.)

Next day, the above vacuum dried azide (0.27 g.) was dissolved in dry ethanol (5 c.c.) and refluxed for one and half hours when evolution of nitrogen was observed below the boiling point of alcohol. Alcohol was then removed under reduced pressure when crude 5:6-dimethoxy-4-carbethoxyaminocoumarin (0.24 g.) was obtained which on crystallisation from very dilute sulphuric acid was obtained as white needles, m.p. 127-28°. (Found: C, 57.44; H, 5.22. $C_{14}H_{15}O_6N$ requires C, 57.33; H, 5.11%). The i.r. spectrum showed urethane carbonyl absorption at 5.92 μ and lactone carbonyl absorption at 5.80 μ and -NH absorption at 3.05 μ .

Reaction of 5:6-Dimethoxy-4-carbethoxyaminocoumarin with Conc. Hydrochloric Acid: Crude 5:6-dimethoxy-4-carbethoxyaminocoumarin (0.15 g.) was decomposed by refluxing for one hour with concentrated hydrochloric acid (2.5 c.c.). On cooling, the mixture was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was extracted with sodium hydroxide solution (1%). The alkaline layer was acidified with hydrochloric acid. This was extracted with ether, dried ($MgSO_4$) and on evaporation a gummy mass was obtained which after triturating with alcohol gave crystalline product (0.01 g.). It was soluble in sodium hydroxide solution (1%) and did not give a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. It showed wine red colour with $FeCl_3$ solution. On purification by sublimation under vacuum, it had m.p. 115°. (Found: C, 62.93; H, 5.30; N, 5.74%). (Carbonyl absorption at 5.78 μ).

Arylidene Derivatives of 4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin: An equimolecular mixture of 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin and the aromatic aldehyde was dissolved in acetic acid and the mixture heated with the addition of a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. On cooling, the arylidene derivatives separated which were collected and crystallised from acetic acid as given in the following Table I.

Condensation of 4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin with Zincke's aldehyde: 4-Keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.16 g.), Zincke's aldehyde¹⁷ (0.26 g.) and dry pyridine (1 c.c.) were heated on water bath for six hours. On cooling, dark violet crystals, m.p. 266° separated which were collected and crystallised from pyridine as shining dark violet crystals, m.p. 270-72° (decomp.). (Found: C, 59.25; H, 3.23. $C_{10}H_{13}O_7N_3$ requires C, 58.96; H, 3.19%).

6'-Methoxyindeno (2',3':3:4) isocoumarin: *m*-Methoxybenzylidene 4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (50 c.c.) was hydrogenated with palladised charcoal (0.05 g.; 10%). The hydrogenation was complete in 15 minutes when only one mole of hydrogen was absorbed. After filtration, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure when 3-(*m*-methoxybenzyl)-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin was obtained as thick oil in nearly quantitative yield giving a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 210° (from alcohol). (Found: N, 11.99. $C_{22}H_{18}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.13%).

17. V. Th. Zincke *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1904, **330**, 367; 1904, **333**, 296; 1905, **338**, 107.
N. I. Fisher and F. M. Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 189.

TABLE I

S.N.	Compound	Melting point	Molecular Formula	Analysis.	
				Found	Calc.
1.	Benzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin	Yellow wooly needles, m.p. 179-80°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃	C, 77.02 H, 4.21	76.81 4.00%
2.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Light yellow needles, m.p. 194-95°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₅ N	C, 65.10 H, 3.10	65.09 3.05%
3.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Light yellow prism, m.p. 234°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₅ N	C, 65.10 H, 3.00	65.09 3.05%
4.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Lemon yellow needles, m.p. 255°.	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₅ N	C, 64.99 H, 3.21	65.09 3.05%
5.	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Light yellow needles, m.p. 155°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₃ Cl	C, 67.51 H, 3.20	67.48 3.16%
6.	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Golden yellow prisms, m.p. 210°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₃ Cl	C, 67.32 H, 3.10	67.48 3.16%
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Pale yellow plates, m.p. 199-20°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₃ Cl	C, 67.50 H, 2.91	67.48 3.16%
8.	<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Yellow needles, m.p. 194°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₄	C, 72.61 H, 4.30	72.85 4.28%
9.	Veratrylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Brown needles, m.p. 227-28°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₃	C, 69.49 H, 4.70	69.68 4.51%
10.	<i>m</i> -Methylbenzylidene-4-keto-3:4-dihydroisocoumarin.	Yellow needles, m.p. 155°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃	C, 77.30 H, 4.49	77.27 4.54

The above reduced product was heated and stirred vigorously at 80° for two hours with polyphosphoric acid (10.0 g. of phosphorus pentoxide and 10.0 c.c. of phosphoric acid). The whole mass was then poured into cracked ice and extracted with ether. The etheral solution was thoroughly washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried (MgSO₄). On evaporation of the solvent, 6'-Methoxyindeno (2',3':3,4) isocoumarin was obtained as a semi-solid mass. On crystallisation from benzene, it was obtained as dull yellow needles, (0.04 g.) m.p. 200°. (Found; C, 77.80; H, 4.82. C₁₇H₁₃O₃ requires C, 77.27; H, 4.54%). ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 238, 288, 368 m μ ; log, 4.21, 3.69, 3.57). The i.r. spectrum showed lactone carbonyl absorption at 5.88 μ .

6'-Methoxyindeno (2', 3': 3, 4) isocarbostryl: The above indenoisocoumarin (0.50 g.) was heated with alcoholic ammonia (2 c.c.; saturated at 0°) on water bath for four hours and then left overnight at room temperature. On working up in the usual manner, the isocarbostryl was crystallised from ethyl alcohol as plates, m.p. 280° (decomp.). (Found: C, 77.70; H, 4.80, N, 5.32. C₁₇H₁₃O₂N requires C, 77.55; H, 4.98, N, 5.10%).